

THE MOTIF OF LONELINESS IN FICTION WORKS

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Annotation : This article illustrates the interpretation of the motif of loneliness in fiction. This situation, characteristic of the human psyche, is used in fiction to reveal human psychology and to shed light on human natural inclinations. In Albert Camus's story "The Stranger", loneliness leads to alienation from society, while in "The Count of Monte Cristo" by Alexandre Dumas, it is revealed that a person can be saved from loneliness by a fellow human being. In "Chess Novel" by Stefan Zweig, books and chess save a person from loneliness. In Khurshid Dustmuhammad's short story "Alone" it is analyzed that the Jadids, in particular, Kadiri's concern for the fate of society alone, lack of intellectuals who awaken the people; in the short story "Loneliness" by Ulugbek Hamdam, the content of our analysis is the tendency of a person to be alone and at the same time he cannot live apart from society.

Key words : motif of loneliness, alienation, tendency to loneliness, psyche, society, press, imprisonment, chess, book, interlocutor.

As the main theme of literature is to illuminate the human and his/her destiny, although the plots are different, the essence of all the works reflects life. Today, in the world literature, great importance is attached not to the physical activity of a person, but to the states of the subconscious, mental and psychological states, the depth of imagination and thinking. As a result of research, it has been determined that the human psyche is more prone to loneliness. It has been proven in science that when a person is alone, the power of imagination and thinking increases several times compared to other people. Tendency to loneliness also causes separation from society, indifference to the fate of society. This is the main content of the story "The Stranger" by the French writer Albert Camus. It is not for nothing that the play begins as follows: "I don't know if my mother died today or tomorrow." [A. Camus. Stranger. page 5] From the first sentence of the play, we witness how unloving and indifferent the main character Meursault is. It is said that the reason he put his mother in the orphanage was because he could not talk to her. He says that he will spend half a day visiting her. He doesn't even know exactly how old his mother is. With this, when he is a stranger to affection, when his boss offers him a job in Paris, or when Marie asks if she wants to marry me, she replies that I don't care. When the judge asked him why he killed the Arab, we

can see how indifferent he is to his own fate from his ridiculous answer, "The sun was shining in my eyes." If society and human relations are alien to Meursault, he himself is alien to the society of people who live on the basis of hypocrisy, avoiding the truth. He will say everything he thinks in court. It's not hypocrisy to make people look good. Meursault does not try to justify himself when his acquaintances, Raimon, Salman, the director of the orphanage, the doorman, old Perez, and others, sentenced him to death based on the testimony of the old man. Meursault is alienated not only from society but also from God. He says to Kashish, "I don't want to waste my time for God's sake". Why is the hero of Camus so indifferent to the people around him, even to his own life? Perhaps this is because he lived without realizing the connection between society and himself. Society is made up of people, if Meursault isn't a part of it, then who is he? That is why the title of the work is called "Stranger". At the time, the writer's ideas about alienation were strongly opposed. They called it "absurd". Years later, the world recognized that there was truth in the work that was condemned as nonsense. Humanity's spirit is fading. When this spirit weakens, a person will fall. German philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche called this subjugation "alienation". People of science - "is there a power that can restore this soul?" Nietzsche answered "will power". Through this, a person can change not only his inner world, but also the external environment. What does Nietzsche mean by this? "Overcoming indifference, finding one's place in society, and maintaining the eternal connection between people, all this is in the hands of a person," he says. So why was Meursault alienated from society? The reason is that he was isolated first, as a result of which other situations arose: crime, unkindness, indifference, etc. Meursault lives alone, he is alone at work, even if he does not pay attention to official dealings. That's why he thinks only of himself and not of others. In the end, he stopped thinking about himself. Only the natural process - the instinct to live - remains in him. He is afraid of only one moment in prison, that is, when they will take him to the execution in the morning, when this moment passes, he is happy. The reason for the joy was that he had one more day to live. However, he spends this day in solitude, waiting for the horror of tomorrow morning.

In the play, the detective refers to Meursault as Mr. Antichrist. That is, this is a reference to the signs of the end of time. It is known that Dajjal is one of the signs of the end times. This work is not called "European caricature" for nothing. France occupies a central place in this. It is said that the signs of the end of time have already appeared here.

That is, people are so indifferent to each other. When Seles was asked in court, "What kind of man do you think Meursault is," he answered, "Yes, a man, an ordinary man." What does he mean by that? Meursault is not the only one who doesn't appreciate his mother, everyone does. What interests him most is his relationship with Marie, although this is not unusual for Europe. The writer wants to say that important relationships have lost their importance. "They are atheists, that's why they don't believe in God, that's why all these problems arise, that's why people like Meursault are growing. Why did Meursault get into this situation? Why didn't others get into this situation, when everyone's situation is the same? Because Meursault does not know lies, Meursault does not know hypocrisy. Meursault is the best representative of the people in this European caricature. Well, if this best representative is condemned to death, what are the rest condemned to? The rest are sentenced to the end times.

The chairman of the court says that Mersoni will be beheaded in the open field. Why the French people? Because the French people are in the worst condition in Europe. By this, the writer wants to say that the public knows that your situation is no less than Meursault's, and in the end, your situation will end with death. It ends with death, which does not leave any possibility. It is not for nothing that we touched on this topic above, when a person is alone, when difficulties fall on his head, his only companion is undoubtedly Allah. But Meursault does not know God, does not believe in him, that is why he became a victim of loneliness. Meursault: "It was when there was a chance to escape from death. Even if they put me in a dry tree and say that you will live here, I will live there." [A. Camus. Stranger. page 79]

We can compare it with the thoughts of Raskolnikov, the hero of the novel "Crime and Punishment" by the Russian writer F. Dostoyevsky: "If I were to be thrown out on a cliff, where only one foot could fit, the sun would be burning above me. "Even though I prefer this life to death," he says. He is freed and confesses his crime and eventually returns to society.

"Chess Novel" by the Austrian writer Stefan Zweig tells about the tenacity of a prisoner who struggled with loneliness. He dreams of finding even one book in his prison cell. One day he finds a booklet about chess games in his cell. The hero of the play reads this book over and finally memorizes it. He plays each chess game in his mind. In the end, he is playing chess with himself in his mind. He doesn't even realize how much time he spends in this activity. His years in prison are enjoyable. When he is released from prison, he becomes an unrivaled grandmaster. This is how the hero of the play overcomes loneliness.

In the novel "The Count of Monte Cristo" by the French writer Alexandre Dumas, we observe the struggle of Edmond Dantes, who was innocently imprisoned in the castle of If. It reaches such a point that he is at the point of committing suicide. At first he wants to hang himself from the window, then he decides to starve to death. He decides not to eat the food brought by the prison officer. So what brought him back to life? It was Abbot Faria's mistaken attempt to open a hole in Edmon's room instead of the street side. Edmon found himself an interlocutor, a colleague, a colleague. Only then did he overcome all the trials and get rid of loneliness. Another symbol of loneliness in the story "The Stranger" is the character of the old man Salamano. He has also been attached to his companion dog for eight years alone. One day his dog goes missing. He looks for the dog a lot, he says that he is used to it, it is tight.

We find a similar situation in the novel "Three Brothers" by the German writer Erich Maria Remarque. One of Frao Zalevsky's tenants is a widow, separated from her husband and two sons in the war, who has since become attached to her cat. Because he took a cat with him to get rid of loneliness. Works reflecting the role of loneliness in human psychology are also found in Uzbek literature. In particular, this passage is given as an epigraph to Ulugbek Hamdam's short story "Loneliness":

I'm in pieces, where are you?

The abyss in my heart, where are you?

I'm falling, where are you?

I'm so lonely, where are you?

I fell to pieces, where are you? [U. Hamdam. Loneliness page 3]

Loneliness is an intimate process unique to a certain person. In it, a person is as free as he wants, he can argue with his heart. The hero of this work, which is told from the language of a twenty-eight-year-old man, has two people living in his body, just like Harry Haller, the hero of Herman Hesse's novel "Desert Wolf". That is, if the soul seeks divine love, then the body follows worldly desires. The hero pours out what is on his tongue as much as he can, and does not exaggerate. Because he was alone. As Herman Hesse, the famous German writer and winner of the international "Nobel" prize, said: "Loneliness is shame." [H. Hesse. page 87] That is, when a person is alone, he is as free as he wants, but sometimes he wants someone to take him out of this loneliness. Because a person cannot be separated from society. The hero of the play also falls into this situation. He says, "Even if a gang of robbers opened the door and came in, I would greet the guests and give them the things they wanted."

The motif of loneliness is used in fiction in two ways. One is to be alone with oneself or to be forced into solitude, and the other is to fight alone for the fate of society, for the homeland, for enlightenment. Both of these situations are expressed in the story "Alone" by the famous writer Khurshid Dustmuhammad. The story tells about the events of Abdullah Kadiri's imprisonment in 1926. In particular, for the article "A Collection of Rumors" published in "Mushtum" magazine, that is, in it, the leaders of Uzbekistan are imprisoned on charges of discrediting the USSR and nationalism. In the work, the writer shows Kadiri's lonely situation, as well as his lonely concern for society. One of the neighbor girls watching Kadiri in the play says, "He must be a bad person, he writes non-stop. Fortunately, his partner says I don't know how to write, thank God." Or teacher Ishaq shows his fist and says, "A fist is not a piece of paper like a table. When you write on it, where do you write it, what do you write?" Kadiri explains to him that "Mushtum" is not a person's fist, it is a kind of newspaper called a magazine. Well, if teacher Ishaq, who studied in Bukhara madrasas and considers himself to be a consultant of the society, says so, then what can be expected from others. Kadiri considers the press to be the only way to save the people from this ignorance. He wants to wake up the people through the press. Through the work, the writer wants to say that people like Kadiri, who tried to open the eyes of the people, were lonely.

In short, since the main subject of fiction is man, his mental state becomes the basis for discussions and comparisons in the interpretation of literary scholars. The motif of loneliness, which is a part of this state of mind, has been observed in various forms in the literature of different nations and we have compared and analyzed it.

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